

AUTHORS PROCLAMATION

Prior to this release, the present manuscript (Frewer et al. (2014a), with minor changes in the main text and without Appendix A, C, D & E) was submitted to a high ranked journal X for fluid mechanics and got reviewed by four independent referees. Based on the reviewers conclusions in not being enough in the focus of the journal, the responsible editor advised us to publish in a different journal. This circumstance compelled us to support the current discussion on open peer review. We decided to publish the reviewers reports, which we provide as supplementary material to this article (with permission of the editor of that journal). The reports we present in their complete and unchanged form, partially uncommented, and partially commented by us where necessary. With this step we believe to make the review process more transparent and in turn would be grateful to get further comments and opinions from the research community.

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Referee No.1

The paper provides a critical analysis of the new invariance transformations recently suggested by Oberlack & Rosteck (2010). As far as I am able to understand it, the transformation is simply multiplying all correlation functions by the same factor. Not being a mathematician, I find this 'invariance' totally unphysical, the same as the authors of the present manuscript. Personally, I would not need any proof that the consequences of that 'invariance' are incorrect, but then maybe mathematicians see this differently.

It is hard for me to judge how many people need this critical analysis, but probably some do. Therefore, publication of that critique in some form makes sense. I do not recommend however publication in the present form. It is so verbose that I doubt that many people (except the referee, Oberlack and Rosteck) will finish reading it. It dwells on many trivialities and arcane details. If the text can be shortened at least three times, it may be of interest for X. I think it is doable.

Referee No.2

This paper is really a lengthy comment on a body of published work, authored by Oberlack and collaborators, which has appeared in various journals, including X.

The Oberlack papers evidently claim to have discovered a new scaling symmetry for the statistics of Navier Stokes turbulence. The present paper claims to show that:

1. The proposed symmetry does not agree with numerical data.
2. The proposed symmetry was derived by a misapplication of symmetry group methods.

The first point seems irrefutable, and perhaps that is enough. After all, even symmetries whose derivation seems secure can fail. For example, it is possible to view Kolmogorov's theory as one of a family of scaling symmetries; the Kármán-Howarth equation determines the member of the family that might actually apply. There are no *mathematical* reasons to reject it — Landau's early objection to Kolmogorov's theory was based on *physical* rather than mathematical misgivings — yet the Kolmogorov theory has been found to be increasingly inaccurate for higher order statistics. My point is that in turbulence theory you don't have to make a mistake to be wrong.

The present paper criticizes Oberlack's derivation in various ways. (I have not read any of the Oberlack papers.) One criticism is that one cannot apply symmetry group analysis to an unclosed hierarchy of equations. This seems quite valid. After all, it would seem risky to speculate about the transformation properties of solutions when we don't even know that solutions exist. The other criticism is based on the use of the Hopf equation, or its functional Fourier transform, the Liouville equation. But here we are on equally shaky ground, because both of these equations involve an infinite number of dimensions, and the properties of such equations, even though they are linear, are as obscure as those of the unclosed hierarchies. Most people (including me) find it easier to comprehend the Liouville equation, and I wish the authors could have confined their analysis to that. After all, since the Hopf and Liouville equations are the functional Fourier transformations of one another, any transformation of one must correspond to a unique transformation of the other. The authors do eventually follow this strategy (in Section 4.1) but only after a long discussion of the Hopf equation.

The authors discussion of these two equations reveals what I believe is a fundamental misconception on their part. Without some form of 'coarse-graining', neither the Hopf equation nor the Liouville equation is a true statistical equation. Rather, they are both exact equations for the evolution of the density distribution, in phase space, of an ensemble of turbulent systems, i.e. they are essentially 'passive scalar equations' in infinite dimensional space. This point was made very eloquently by Orszag (1970) (S.A. Orszag, JFM 1970, 41, 363-386).

Moreover, 'coarse-graining' is not something that happens by itself. It must be *imposed*

by introducing extra assumptions analogous to those required to close the infinite moment hierarchy. My overall point is that neither the unclosed hierarchy, nor the Hopf equation, nor the Liouville equation, may be a legitimate candidate for symmetry group analysis.

In summary, the authors' proof, using numerical *data*, that Oberlack's theory is wrong seems appropriate, although it might be more appropriately directed to a journal that accepts comments on work published in that journal. The authors' explanation of *why* Oberlack's theory is wrong seems overly complicated and perhaps unnecessary.

Referee No.3

In view of the importance of non-trivial symmetries, the authors address the very relevant question when such symmetries, in particular when they arise in a 'weaker' form and/or are of a statistical nature, lead to relevant physical results. I consider their work to be of sufficient interest to merit publication. However, I recommend that the authors should consider the comments/questions attached below and revise their paper accordingly. Here are my comments/questions:

1. This work only considers a very specific extension of scale-symmetries when, in addition to time t and space x , further variables are admitted. What about more general space-time transformations, such as conformal transformations (relevant in equilibrium critical phenomena) or 'non-relativistic versions' thereof, such as the Schrödinger algebra? The Schrödinger-invariance of Navier-Stokes at infinite Reynolds number was already known to Ovsiannikov (1982 – based on work published in Russian in the 1960s); rediscovered by Hassaine & Horvathy, *Ann. of Phys.* 282, 218 (2000); O'Raiheartaigh & Sreedhar, *Ann. of Phys.* 293, 215 (2001). More recently, analogous symmetries were sought in 1D Burgers turbulence or in interface growth of the so-called 1D Kardar-Parisi-Zhang universality class, see Ivashkevich, *J. Phys.* A30, L525 (1997); Henkel, Noh, Pleimling, *Phys. Rev.* E85, 030102R (2012); Henkel, *Nucl. Phys.* B869, 282 (2013).

2. Writing down eqn. (2.7): over what ensemble is the average to be taken? Physically, such an equation would be an explicit equation of state, e.g. $T = T(t, x, u, u_{(n)}, \dots)$ to be fully specified. Therefore, insisting on the arbitrary nature of T does not look very meaningful to me. Then either: a given T will tell which symmetries are admissible, if any, or else a given symmetry will provide constraints on admissible forms of T , if any. *[We agree, this is exactly the way it should be done. But Oberlack et al. regard such terms permanently as arbitrary, which forms the center of our critique.]*

3. Indeed, letting certain parameters appear as new variables can be helpful – see e.g. conditional symmetries of a variant of Navier-Stokes equations, Zhang & Horvathy, *Eur. Phys. J.* C65, 607 (2009); Cherniha & Henkel, *J. Math. Anal. Appl.* 369, 120 (2010).

4. Who proposed first the symmetry (4.1)? Please provide a reference. *[Done]*

5. The condition $q \leq 0$ in (4.1) does not allow for an inverse transformation! Therefore, the generator Q does not generate a Lie group, but only an associative product with unit element ($q = 0$), i.e. a so-called semi-group. This restriction should have structural consequences – please comment. *[Done; on the level of the moments it has no consequences.]*

6. In (3.3), what about anomalous transformation of the integration measure $\mathcal{D}u$? Features of this kind are well-known to arise in 2D conformal invariance, see the 'yellow bible' textbook by Di Francesco, Mathieu & Senechal or any other introduction to 2D CFT. They are related to what is called there a 'central charge', which in general only vanishes for mean-field theories. Mathematicians devoted a lot of effort in figuring out just how the functional integral measure transforms under conformal transformations, which infinitesimally is described in terms of the Schwarz derivative. The arguments and the symmetry (4.1) appear to be valid on the un-renormalised tree level – and should therefore be of a mean-field character, in the language of statistical physics.

7. Are you sure that in the Fourier transform (3.3) and its inverse (4.8), you did not omit a factor $(2\pi)^{+/-\infty}$? *[Done; no factor is missing, please see definition (3.5)]*

8. The transformation law (4.16) again looks mean-field to me – in interacting field-theory, u^2 could become a non-trivial composite operator with a non-trivial scaling dimension X_{u^2} , which only above the upper critical dimension has the value $X_{u^2} = 2X_u$.

9. Consistency checks such as presented here go much beyond the example of Navier-Stokes equation and are of potential interest to many cooperative/complex phenomena, in and out of equilibrium. This should be made more explicit and the possible caveats coming from interacting field-theory should be carefully outlined. After all, the Hopf equation is merely some sort of master equation.

10. I found the Principle on p. 18 (before section 4.4) quite obvious: of course, a problem should be completely formulated; yes, the shape of the eqn(s) of state will constrain any possible symmetry ... and so on.

11. In reading the paper, I could not help the impression that the main motivation was to refute a series of papers by Oberlack and collaborators.

12. What is the positive meaning of the symmetry (4.1)? Is it somehow analogous to the supersymmetry people have found since the 1970s in critical dynamics (using the Stratanovich interpretation) and which finally guarantees probability conservation? Not much more has ever come out of it, as far as I am aware ...

Referee No.4

This paper aims to criticize the paper 'New statistical symmetries of the multi-point equations and its importance for turbulent scaling laws' by Oberlack & Rosteck, published in *Discrete Continuous Dyn. Sys.* (2010). In that paper, Oberlack & Rosteck (2010) proposed a scaling transformation group, shown in Eq.(4.4) and Eq.(4.6) in the current paper, which is judged to be physically inconsistent for three reasons. First, Eq.(4.4) leads to a global change of probability density functional P for the velocity field u , but without changing the velocity field $u(t,x)$; this is described to be "completely unphysical and not realized in nature". Second, Eq.(4.4) and Eq.(4.6) implies that n th and $(n+1)$ th correlation functions have the same dilation, which contradicts with Eq.(4.16) assuming that the mean and fluctuating velocity experience the same scaling transformation. Third, the resulted transformation for the correlation functions from Eq.(4.4), i.e. Eq.(4.19), are judged to be superfluous and artificial, because Eq.(4.4) is an oversimplified statistical representation. Therefore the scaling transformation Eq.(4.4) obtained by Oberlack & Rosteck (2010) is misleading.

Furthermore, this paper emphasizes that the resulted scaling laws from Eq.(4.4) have no predictive value, which is supported by an analysis of DNS data of zero-pressure-gradient (ZPG) turbulent boundary layer. Data shows that scaling laws derived from Eq.(4.4) (i.e., $T \circ S_1 \circ S_2 \circ Q_1 \circ Q_2$) only describe a very restricted flow domain, and the parameters in the formulas are quite sensitive. In contrast, without the scaling symmetry Eq.(4.4), scaling laws on the subgroup $(T \circ S_1 \circ S_2)$ agrees with data even better (Fig.3 & Fig.5). As a conclusion, the authors assert that the new statistical scaling laws by Oberlack & Rosteck (2010) are "by no means useful, and should be discarded in future work."

The materials are presented in a clear fashion. However, I am afraid that it is not suitable to be published in X, because of its limited scope: only criticizing Oberlack & Rosteck (2010) is not enough to warrant its publication in X. The paper of Oberlack & Rosteck (2010) is itself not an important paper matching with the standard of X. On the other hand, the main effort of Oberlack & Rosteck (2010) to connect scaling laws with Lie group analysis is worthwhile, despite some misleading statements, because the theoretical description of wall turbulence badly needs new ideas and new methods. The challenge is around over a century, and it is time to make a definite progress. The authors seem to agree at this point, since they motivate a fitting procedure with DNS data from a scaling symmetry analysis. Unfortunately, the authors have put the wrong emphasis on

criticizing a previous (not very important) paper, instead of addressing the key issue how to use constructively the scaling symmetry analysis for achieving a global description of the mean quantities.

A particular point raised by the authors regarding equivalence versus symmetry transformation is rather misleading. *[To avoid this we extended Section 2 and included Appendix A & C. With this step we believe to have clarified all uncertainties which will be mentioned by the referee from this point onwards.]* This argument is evoked to provide a theoretical basis to criticize Oberlack & Rosteck (2010), since Eq.(4.4) is judged to follow an equivalence transformation, rather than a symmetry transformation. Then, the authors arbitrarily claim that defining invariant solutions is only well-defined for symmetry transformations, or for closed equations, ruling out any possibility to construct valid solution for unclosed turbulence problem. This qualification is very misleading, and particularly harmful when it is applied to the effort to construct solutions for wall-bounded turbulence problem involving unclosed equations. According to the authors, the equivalence transformation maps a solution of the equations to a solution of another equation (with different parameters) *[No, not only. Apart from Example 1 in Section 2, which the referee addresses here, we also discussed a further example, namely Example 2 which demonstrates the action of an equivalence transformation much more strongly than Example 1],* while the symmetry transformation link two solutions of the same equation. This definition by no means disqualifies the equivalence transformation in finding (or explaining) new solutions of a difficult problem. In fact, the scaling transformations (F.2) and (F.3) used by the authors to derive scaling laws and compare with DNS data are equivalence transformation, but not symmetry transformation, since the DNS data are solution of the Navier-Stokes equation, but the invariance transformation are only admitted by the inviscid Euler equation. *[No, (F.2) and (F.3) are not equivalence transformations of the Navier-Stokes equation. Both transformations are admitted only by the Euler equation and only as pure symmetries (statistically as well as deterministically). They can not be derived from any equivalence transformation of the Navier-Stokes equation, in the way as to first consistently take the viscous case $\nu \neq 0$ before the transformation and to then obtain the inviscid case $\tilde{\nu} = 0$ after the transformation. For example, consider the specific (deterministic) equivalence transformation (2.5): If $\tilde{\nu} = 0$ then also $\nu = 0$ (and vice versa), i.e. we perfectly remain in the inviscid Euler formulation in being entirely unable to establish a connection to the viscous Navier-Stokes equation. And, not only for transformation (2.5), which specifically only emerges from the general (deterministic) equivalence transformation (2.4) as the limiting case $f(\nu) = 1$, but also for the two other remaining limiting choices of $f(\nu)$ we face this same issue of unconnectedness too, in that for $\tilde{\nu} = 0$ the transformation (2.4) degenerates either to an identity transformation, if e.g. $f(\nu) \sim \nu$, or to a null transformation, if e.g. $f(\nu) \sim 1/\nu$. In other words, the Navier-Stokes equation (with non-vanishing viscosity) cannot be converted into the Euler equation (with vanishing viscosity) by employing any Lie-group transformation. The deeper reason for this is that the well-known challenging issues related to the vanishing (anomalous) viscosity limit $\nu \rightarrow 0$ in transiting from the viscous Navier-Stokes to the inviscid Euler equations, particularly for bounded flows, also resides in every Lie group analysis for variable transformations, in that the limit is singularly unstable for symmetry transformations and degenerative, non-unique and thus non-existent for equivalence transformations (see also Ibragimov, Kovalev (2009), *Approximate and Renormgroup Symmetries*, Springer Verlag).]* When dealing with unclosed equations, there is indeed a problem of arbitrariness in defining group parameters, but the logic of devaluating the scaling analysis of unclosed equations is totally destructive and meaningless. Instead of making distinctions between the equivalence and symmetry transformation, it would be more valuable to provide a constructive example of deriving analytic solutions from (either equivalence or symmetry) scaling analysis.

The authors seem to agree that the important task of a symmetry analysis is to extract valuable information from the general structure of the solution manifold, e.g. to

generate invariant or self-similar solutions, then the criticism in page 7 that "they must be carefully interpreted as only being functional relations or functional complexes which stay invariant under the derived equivalence group, and not as being solutions of the associated underdetermined system, as done, for example ..." is rather excessive. In fact, Oberlack (2001) has carefully interpreted the scaling laws obtained from group invariance as 'candidate invariant solution' for the unclosed systems, but not classical solution for ODE/PDE. *[Correct. However, on the other side, Oberlack (2001) claims to have derived both the logarithmic law of the wall, as well as other specific scaling laws as first principle solutions, namely as solutions emerging directly from the Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations by exploiting symmetries in a Lie group approach, which, by closer inspection, is a misleading statement. Because, in its key step the symmetry analysis performed in Oberlack (2001) cannot be reproduced. Instead, a completely different result is obtained when repeating the investigation correctly, which even demands an opposite conclusion than Oberlack (2001) claims (Frewer et al., 2014b).]* Moreover, She et al. (2011) have also noted that, for the unclosed systems, the rationality of 'invariant solution' assumed by group invariance, needs to be confirmed by comparing with numerical solution of Navier-Stokes equation (i.e. DNS data). At this stage, attempt to derive empirical solutions from symmetry analysis needs to be encouraged.

In conclusion, despite the fact that I agree with the statement that Eq.(4.4) is meaningless, the scope of the paper is too limited and its outcomes are not important enough to be published in X. I recommend that the authors submit a variant of this paper to other journals, or as a comment to Discrete Continuous. Dyn. Sys. (Oberlack & Rostock, 2010).

References

- FREWER, M., KHUJADZE, G. & FOYSI, H. 2014*a* On the physical inconsistency of a new statistical scaling symmetry in incompressible Navier-Stokes turbulence. *arXiv:1412.3061*.
- FREWER, M., KHUJADZE, G. & FOYSI, H. 2014*b* Is the log-law a first principle result from Lie-group invariance analysis? A comment on the Article by Oberlack (2001). *arXiv:1412.3069*.